

Interactive Multimedia Stories and Comprehension Skills of Grade Two Learners

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of teaching through interactive multimedia. It also sought to determine the magnitude of the effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the comprehension skills of the research subjects. The study was conducted at Santa Cruz Central Elementary School, Santa Cruz South District, in the Division of Davao del Sur. There were 50 grade two learners who served as respondents in this study: 25 were from Section A, the control group, and 25 were from Section B, the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous, meaning that both learners from Sections A and B had identical grades. This study utilized the non-random assignment of subjects, where all learners in Sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. The study employed the new normal learning modality, which was blended learning where the teacher provided modules while also meeting the learners online, adhering to the protocols of the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher met the learners online for follow-up sessions on what had been printed in the modules. This study revealed that the utilization of interactive multimedia stories increased the comprehension skills of grade two learners. It also revealed the magnitude of the difference between the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Interactive multimedia stories 2. Comprehension skills 3. Technology

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1. Introduction

Technology has transformed and reshaped the world of education. Language pedagogy has constantly changed as technological advancements came into the limelight. Language students nowadays have easy access to literary works, novels, short tales, poems, and teaching materials. The current explosion of multimedia narrative applications on touch-based devices (e.g., iPads) has the potential to aid in the literacy development of elementary pupils. The embedded multimedia and touch-interactive features of multimedia stories, such as music, animation, zooming in/out effects, and touch-initiated feedback, have the potential to allow youngsters to access rich contextual information autonomously and actively make meaning of words and tale content (Verhallen Bus, 2010). According to (Kledecka Nadera, 2001), reading texts can be modified using computer software packages that allow for the addition of sound, images, photos, animations, video, and a direct link to dictionaries for improved understanding and comprehension. These computer technologies bring the target language to life and make

it more tangible (Warschauer & Healey, 1998). These devices also help language learners improve their listening, speaking, reading, writing, grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary skills. Reading is a fundamental communicative ability, but it involves a lengthy process. Reading comprehension is the process of determining what information the author provides in the written frame. In this scenario, reading can be defined as intelligently handling, checking, and asking questions about the text. According to (Leonard, 2003), reading is nothing more than "spelling" that relates sound and image, but Robert Karim (1980) defines reading as a handle that directs the creator's thinking. According to the comprehension hypothesis, compelling understanding in the EFL classroom is based on the relationship between show data and dynamic interactive multimedia (Nadirah et al.), and persuasive communication is based on the degree to which the audience and speakers share a semantic "field" (Buhler, 1908). When preparing understudies for a reading activity, we can help them become aware of significant prior information while determining whether or not that information is sufficient for content understanding. Furthermore, at that time, we will be able to make informed selections concerning reading assignments and training, as well as related topics (Langer, 1981). Given that teachers only utilize traditional teaching methods in the classroom, the researcher came up with the notion of using a new technique to teach student reading comprehension—a new technique that can pique students' interest, a technique that can help learners understand the material more easily—a technique used to teach reading that is critical to influencing the student to become a competent reader. According to prior research, a competent educator should enhance their methods or techniques so that students can understand what the teacher is teaching them, and this will have a favorable impact on the students' performance (Romadloni, 2017). Comprehension challenges exist among early-grade learners at Santa Cruz Central Elementary School in the Division of Davao Del Sur. To address this, the researcher aims to implement a long-term goal of using interactive multimedia stories to enhance the reading comprehension of second-grade students. The study will delve into teaching strategies using interactive multimedia. As a teacher within this educational institution, the researcher seeks to explore alternative approaches to tackle this issue. In the landscape of education, the interplay between reading comprehension and interactive multimedia emerges as a crucial area of investigation, offering insights into cognitive processes and pedagogical strategies aimed at enhancing learning outcomes. Reading comprehension, a fundamental skill taught in schools, encompasses the intricate process of extracting meaning from written texts, transcending mere decoding to encompass interpretation, critical thinking, and inference-making (Eyres, 2021). Simultaneously, the advent of interactive multimedia has transformed educational practices, providing dynamic platforms that integrate various media formats to engage learners and facilitate knowledge acquisition (Mayer, 2019). Within this dynamic educational milieu, a vast body of literature has delved into the individual components and instructional methodologies related to reading comprehension and interactive multimedia. By synthesizing and critically analyzing this corpus of research, this review seeks to offer a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationship between reading comprehension and interactive multimedia in educational contexts. Reading is a foundational skill that is integral to the educational process, encompassing more than the simple act of decoding symbols. It involves an active process where readers generate meaning from the text rather than merely receiving information (Eyres, 2021). This perspective underscores the complexity of reading, highlighting that readers

actively attempt to comprehend the meaning of written or printed words through word recognition, literal understanding, interpretation, and critical/creative thinking skills. According to Anderson et al. (2020), reading involves deciphering the meaning of written texts through the coordination of several interconnected sources of information. Walter R. Smith's assertion that "Reading is what the reader does to gain the meaning he requires from printed sources" (Slope, 2020) aligns with this active view of reading. Fellow L. Bond and Eva Bond Wagner (2021) describe reading as "the process of understanding an author's meaning, translating it, evaluating it, and acting upon it," while F. Dubin (2021) emphasizes the cognitive nature of reading, describing it as primarily a cognitive process with the brain performing most of the work. The primary goal of reading is to understand the text, and comprehension is a participatory process. Anderson (2023) describes reading comprehension as a negotiation and understanding process between the reader and the writer, heavily involving prior knowledge and language skills. This negotiation process means that readers expect texts to make sense, particularly in academic settings. Research shows that individual differences in decoding and linguistic ability significantly influence reading comprehension across numerous languages. These components' relative influence changes over time, with decoding being more closely linked to reading comprehension in early development and linguistic knowledge becoming a stronger predictor as decoding skills are mastered (Catts, 2022; Catts, Adlof, Weismer, 2023). As learners grow older, inference-making becomes more critical than vocabulary for comprehension (Cromley et al., 2019; Ahmed et al., 2022). Vocabulary, inference-making, and background information all impact reading comprehension from adolescence to young adulthood, both directly and indirectly. During the construction phase, textual information and reader knowledge are automatically activated. Activation extends throughout the memory network during the integration phase, settling on concepts with higher activation and more linkages to other concepts while suppressing weakly linked concepts. This iterative process, as outlined in Kintsch's construction-integration (CI) model, enables readers to combine information from the text with their prior knowledge to form a coherent mental representation of the text (Kintsch, 2019). The complexities of comprehension are underscored by numerous linguistic abilities, cognitive processes, and knowledge sources, making instructional targeting challenging (Perfetti Adlof, 2021). Effective reading comprehension components should be integral to the process, vary across individuals, and be suitable for instructional intervention (Perfetti Adlof, 2021). This review focuses on four key components of reading comprehension—vocabulary, inference, knowledge, and comprehension monitoring—that play prominent roles in understanding text and represent potential instructional targets. While emphasizing higher-order comprehension skills, we also acknowledge the foundational role of efficient word recognition (Perfetti Stafura, 2019). Vocabulary is a robust predictor of reading comprehension throughout development. Children acquire vocabulary at an impressive rate, averaging 2 to 8 root words per day (National Reading Panel, 2020). Once children begin independent reading, vocabulary acquisition relies more on exposure to print than on oral language or instruction (Hayes Ahrens, 1988). Explicit instruction accounts for only a fraction of the vocabulary needed for high school graduation, with most words learned implicitly through repeated exposure in various contexts (Stahl Nagy, 2020). Significant individual differences in vocabulary size exist among early readers and persist through elementary school. By the end of second grade, disadvantaged students can lag up to two years behind their average peers and

four years behind those in the upper quartile in vocabulary knowledge. Emphasizing early and continued vocabulary learning is crucial, though it's unclear if explicit instruction alone can bridge the gap sufficiently to impact general comprehension. Reviews on the impact of vocabulary instruction on comprehension found gains in measures containing the taught words, but not for general comprehension measures (Compton, 2019). Less skilled readers benefit more from vocabulary instruction than typical readers, highlighting the importance of vocabulary for these students (Elleman et al., 2019). Interactive multimedia in the EFL classroom has evolved significantly. According to the Modern Oxford American Lexicon, multimedia in computer applications incorporates sound and video interactively, while in craftsmanship or instructional frameworks, it uses multiple media of expression or communication. This interaction involves an exchange of information that evolves over time. The definition's usage of the words "expression" and "communication" implies the presence of interacting activities. In that sense, communication can be seen as an interactive process between two persons exchanging information and evolving or changing as a result. The term multimedia is used to describe a very broad area that includes informatics, telecommunications, the audio-visual production industry, film, and digital media. Today, multimedia encompasses informatics, telecommunications, the audio-visual industry, film, and digital media. "Interactive multimedia" refers to a field where various media facilitate expression or communication, allowing for content and context alteration (Laurillard, 2021). When "interactive" is used in conjunction with two entities, it signifies mutual influence. This can manifest physically or as a change in the user's mental state, often coexisting, especially when viewed over time. For example, a painter's interaction with their tools and canvas evolves into a finished work that continues to interact

with viewers emotionally and intellectually. Despite the fact that these forms come to an end for the artist when the painting is finished, the medium itself continues to interact when another person is affected, motivated, or moved by the painting. This may result in a bodily response prompted by the want to capture the image or purchase a replica or genuine workmanship, which may then be a client as the starting point for modern intelligent behavior. Furthermore, in *Modern Media Expressions*, this instinctively prepared commonly includes several media. The phrase "Interactive Multimedia" can refer to a genuine or advanced framework in which various media or humans interact with one another through their intelligent behavior. When the term "interactive multimedia" is used in domains like craftsmanship or education, it implies the employment of various media for expression or communication, as well as the presence of an active user-state or content-altering capability. Interactive media, any computer-delivered electronic system that allows the user to control, combine, and manipulate different types of media, such as text, sound, video, computer graphics, and animation. Interactive media integrate computer, memory storage, digital (binary) data, telephone, television, and other information technologies. Their most common applications include training programs, video games, electronic encyclopedias, and travel guides. Interactive media shift the user's role from observer to participant and are considered the next generation of electronic information systems. Interactive media has done more to change school curriculum and practices than nearly anything else—and in such a short amount of time. While it can be hard to keep up with every trend in educational technology, the mindset you have when it comes to classroom tech matters just as much as which ones you use. By learning to view it as a means of enhancing your lessons and resources, you can provide your students with tools and opportunities they

may not otherwise access. Interactive multimedia is defined as a computer-delivered electronic system enabling users to control, combine, and manipulate different media types like text, sound, video, computer graphics, and animation. Common applications include training programs, video games, electronic encyclopedias, and travel guides. Interactive media shifts the user's role from observer to participant, marking the next generation of electronic information systems. The integration of multimedia in education has shown potential to enhance learning outcomes. Multimedia learning, which uses text, images, audio, and video to convey information, caters to various learning styles, making education more inclusive and effective (Mayer, 2019). Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML) explains how multimedia supports dual coding theory by engaging both visual and auditory channels, enhancing memory retention and understanding (Sweller, 2020). Interactivity significantly influences student engagement and comprehension. Interactive multimedia allows learners to control their learning pace and path, fostering deeper understanding (Laurillard, 2021). Features like quizzes, hyperlinks, and simulations encourage active learning, which is more effective than passive information consumption (Chi, 2009). Interactive multimedia has been shown to improve comprehension by making learning more dynamic and engaging. A study by (Moreno, 2021) found that interactive multimedia presentations enhance understanding by enabling learners to interact with content meaningfully. Interactive elements help clarify complex concepts, making them easier to grasp and retain. Narrative and storytelling are powerful educational tools that structure knowledge and facilitate retention of complex information. In multimedia, stories provide meaningful context, making abstract concepts more concrete and relatable. Narrative structure aids in organizing information, enhancing comprehension and recall (Graesser et al., 2020). Combining interactivity with storytelling in multimedia formats creates a potent educational tool. Interactive multimedia stories leverage the engaging nature of narratives and the active learning benefits of interactivity. Interactive videos can significantly improve learners' understanding and retention of information by allowing dynamic content engagement (Schwan Riempp, 2021). Studies have shown the effectiveness of interactive multimedia stories in enhancing comprehension skills. (Zhang et al., 2010) found that students using interactive multimedia stories had better comprehension and retention compared to those using traditional texts, emphasizing the role of multimedia in engaging and understanding content. Interactive elements within multimedia stories, such as clickable links, quizzes, and branching scenarios, enhance student engagement. Interactivity transforms passive information consumption into active learning, keeping learners focused and motivated, which improves comprehension (Silverman, 2021). Research by Moreno and Mayer (2007) supports this, showing that interactive multimedia presentations significantly improve comprehension compared to non-interactive formats. Allowing students to control their learning pace leads to deeper comprehension. Vocabulary acquisition, a critical aspect of reading comprehension, can be significantly enhanced through interactive multimedia. Multimedia resources, such as digital flashcards, interactive games, and video content, can provide repeated exposure to new words in various contexts, facilitating implicit vocabulary learning. Tools like interactive e-books and language learning apps often incorporate multimedia elements to reinforce vocabulary through visual and auditory channels, aligning with Mayer's CTML principles (Mayer, 2019). Interactive multimedia can also support the development of inference-making and critical thinking skills. Digital platforms that present texts with integrated questions, branching storylines, and

scenario-based learning can prompt students to make inferences and apply critical thinking. By providing immediate feedback and opportunities for reflection, these multimedia tools help students refine their inferential skills and deepen their comprehension (Chi, 2009). Interactive multimedia can effectively activate and build upon students' prior knowledge and background information, crucial for reading comprehension. Virtual field trips, interactive timelines, and multimedia presentations can provide contextual information that enriches students' understanding of the text. These resources can scaffold learning by connecting new information to existing knowledge frameworks, thereby enhancing comprehension (Schwan Riempp, 2021). Interactive multimedia tools can facilitate comprehension monitoring and promote self-regulated learning. Features like interactive quizzes, progress tracking, and adaptive learning pathways allow students to assess their understanding and adjust their learning strategies accordingly. By fostering metacognitive skills, these tools empower students to take an active role in their learning process, improving overall comprehension (Silverman, 2021). Several empirical studies and case reports highlight the effectiveness of integrating interactive multimedia in reading comprehension instruction. For instance, a study by Moreno and Mayer (2007) demonstrated that students who engaged with interactive multimedia presentations showed significant improvements in comprehension compared to those who used non-interactive formats. Similarly, (Zhang et al.,2010) found that interactive multimedia stories enhanced students' comprehension and retention more effectively than traditional texts. A case study conducted in a middle school setting revealed that the use of interactive multimedia e-books resulted in higher engagement levels and improved reading comprehension scores among students. The multimedia e-books included features like animated illustrations, audio narration, and interactive quizzes, which helped students better understand and retain the content.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—In carrying out this study, the researcher used the quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design is good when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects are an intact group of learners.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Santa Cruz Central Elementary School, Santa Cruz South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were 50 grade two learners 25 were from section A, which would be the controlled group, and 25 were from section B, which would be the exper-

imental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was blended learning, where the teacher gave the module while meeting the learners online while adhering to the protocols of the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow-up session on

what had been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25-item test would eventually determine the reading comprehension skills of the research subjects. The pre-test will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pre-test will be very helpful to assess the reading comprehension skills of grade two learners. On the other hand, post-test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of reading comprehension skills of grade two learners, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale Level	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 – 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 – 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 – 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking permission for this research study to be conducted and was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V, and the school principal of Santa Cruz Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the school division Superin-

tendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts, preferably the experts of the study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in Santa Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered a pre-test to both the controlled

and experimental classes and eventually commenced her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered a post-test to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher would make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The statistical tools to be employed for analyzing and interpreting

the responses in this study include the mean, which will illustrate the level of reading comprehension skills of second-grade learners based on both pre-test and post-test scores. Additionally, Eta squared will be used to assess the impact of the interactive multimedia stories approach on the reading comprehension skills of second-grade learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship between the Pre-test and Post-test Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade two

learners. The control group got a mean of 14.64 or Beginning, while the experimental group got a mean of 15.31 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group (Pre-test)	25	14.64	Beginning (58.56)
Experimental Group (Pre-test)	25	15.31	Beginning (60.24)

The table shows that during the pre-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group, although both belong to the Beginning level. This finding is congruent with the idea of Eyres (2021), who said that Reading is a complex act that entails much more than decoding symbols. According to Eyres' perspective, reading is a complex process in which readers actively generate meaning from the text rather than only receiving information. The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning

(CTML) by Mayer (2001) provides a robust framework for understanding how multimedia impacts learning. According to CTML, multimedia presentations support dual coding theory by engaging both visual and auditory channels, which can enhance memory retention and understanding. Furthermore, multimedia can reduce cognitive load by presenting information in a more digestible format, thereby improving comprehension (Sweller, 2020).

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade two learners. The control group got a mean of 20.37, or Developing, while the experimental group gained a mean of 21.78 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from

the table that during the post-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.47 from a mean rating of 15.31 to 21.78. This means that the experimental group has a far bet-

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group (Post-test)	25	20.37	Developing (81.48)
Experimental Group (Post-test)	25	21.78	Approaching Proficiency (87.12)

ter performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent with Laurillard’s (2021) idea that interactivity is a crucial component of multimedia learning that significantly influences student engagement and comprehension. Interactive multimedia allows learners to control their learning pace and path, fostering a deeper understanding (Laurillard, 2021). Interactive features such as quizzes, hyperlinks, and simulations encourage active learning, which is more effective than passive consumption of

information (Chi, 2009). Interactive multimedia has been shown to improve comprehension skills by making learning more dynamic and engaging. A study by Moreno (2021) demonstrated that interactive multimedia presentations could enhance understanding by allowing learners to interact with content in meaningful ways. The use of interactive elements helps to clarify complex concepts, making them easier to grasp and retain.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	36	-5.36	.0343	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.36 with a p-value of .0343, which is less than the .05 level of significance, which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post-test scores of the grade two learners. This implies that the use of interactive multimedia stories in teaching grade two learners has contributed to the effectiveness of comprehension skills, which is revealed by the scores of the grade two learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Graesser et al. (2020) who said that narrative and storytelling have long been recognized as powerful educational tools. Stories help structure knowledge

and facilitate the retention of complex information. In the context of multimedia, stories can provide a meaningful context for learning, making abstract concepts more concrete and relatable. The narrative structure aids in organizing information, which enhances comprehension and recall. Combining interactivity with storytelling in multimedia formats creates a potent educational tool. Interactive multimedia stories leverage the engaging nature of narratives and the active learning benefits of interactivity. Interactive videos can significantly improve learners’ understanding and retention of information by allowing them to engage with content dynamically (Schwan and Riempp, 2021).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade Two Pupils

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
50	-4.36	0.442	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of interactive multimedia stories on the comprehension skills of grade two learners. It generated an Eta² value of 0.442, which signifies a large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in designing effective interactive multimedia stories for grade two learners. Effective multimedia stories not only improve immediate understanding but also foster long-term retention and the ability to apply knowledge in real-world contexts. Interactive elements within multimedia stories, such as clickable links, quizzes, and branching scenarios, play a crucial role in

enhancing student engagement. Interactivity transforms the passive consumption of information into an active learning experience. When learners interact with the content, they are more likely to stay focused and motivated, which enhances their understanding of the material (Silverman, 2021). Research by Moreno and Mayer (2007) supports this, showing that interactive multimedia presentations significantly improve comprehension compared to non-interactive formats. The ability to control the pace and path of learning allows students to process information at their speed, leading to deeper understanding.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the researcher’s findings, conclusions, and recommendations after analyzing and interpreting the findings. This study sought to determine the effect of interactive multimedia stories on the comprehension skills of grade two learners. This study used a quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design is good when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects were intact learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 50 grade two learners 25 from section A, which comprised the controlled group, and 25 from section B, which comprised the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous, so pupils of sections A and B have identical ranges of performance. This study used non-random assignment of subjects, where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of interactive multimedia stories has increased the comprehension skills of grade two learners. It also revealed a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners in both the controlled and experimental groups are at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level, while the post-test scores of

the experimental group are at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. *Recommendations*—In light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: Teachers teaching grade two learners should use interactive multimedia stories to fur-

ther develop their comprehension skills. Multimedia stories create a dynamic and inclusive learning atmosphere by engaging multiple senses, providing interactive and contextual learning experiences, and catering to diverse learning needs. The school heads should promote interactive multimedia stories as a strategy for offering students a narrative that combines text, audio, video, and interactive elements. These stories are not only engaging but also significantly enhance comprehension skills.

A school policy about the utilization of interactive multimedia stories can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demonstrate teaching during the LAC session using interactive multimedia stories as a teaching strategy. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study be conducted on the use of interactive multimedia stories as a teaching strategy. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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